

THE PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *this article study the challenges that teachers face while teaching English language. Teaching English as a foreign language is a demanding task, especially when it is done in settings where the English language distributes a very limited purpose. This article paper is important to highlight and investigate the challenges of teaching English and the viewpoint of English language teachers in facing the challenges of teaching English in the classroom. A number of challenges rebelled, partly from students, partly from teachers and partly from the school facility.*

Key words: *challenges, factors, provocation, distribution, technical knowledge, solution, methods.*

Teaching English as a foreign language refers to teaching English to students whose first language is not English. Teaching English as a foreign language usually occurs in the students or pupils own country, either within the state school system or private ones, in an after-hours language school or with a teacher. As a foreign language, there are so many things that make it quite hard to teach and, one of them is the subjection. English is a language that must be exposed or practiced many times. As a foreign language, using English language is a provocation for students because they cannot use it all the time and in all the places. The other thing is the This research paper is salient to highlight the challenges of teaching English the struggles of teachers and students that they face during teaching or learning the second

language the detriment of appropriate solutions to it. In addition, it is attempts to investigate the challenges in teaching English as foreign language at school in the world. This paper also intends to show how pre-service teacher education would benefit from an interdisciplinary approach with a combination of declarative knowledge and technical knowledge with all teaching being ‘science-based. Moreover, different factors such as poor parental support, lack of students’ and parents’ support, lack of learning/teaching materials at schools, both students’ and parents’ negative attitude towards learning English, lack of motivation and proper guidance, lack of interest in learning English, poor learning environment, poor family background and lower level of basic knowledge in English which contribute to the challenges faced by the teachers in teaching English at rural schools.

Limited access to resources

There are many types of educational resources that can help teachers deliver lessons in a better way. Some examples of resources commonly available for English teachers include: Wi-Fi, projector, copier, textbooks, whiteboards, computers, other technologies (such as CD players), art supplies, and educational posters. Teachers may find themselves completely without these resources, or they may end up in a situation where supply is limited or not working properly .and this lack of equipment hinder teachers to embody an effective teaching process puts forward that “language could only be understood by practicing all the four skills; listening, speaking, reading, and writing”.

Wrong syllabus to be taught

The syllabus is a kind of content that the teachers follow to teach to the students. The syllabus plays a very important role in teaching the English language and also in other subjects. The syllabus helps the teachers to prepare the important factors of the course and organized the overall course to teach to the student’s step by step. Mostly the teachers faced this problem in teaching the English language. The wrong syllabus is given to them to teach the students the English language. The teachers teach the

wrong syllabus will make negative impressions on the students, and by this, the students cannot learn and speak the English language.

Students Disturbed the Class

Sometimes the students get bored and try to do other activities during the lectures which disturbed the teachers during teaching the English language. They try to speak to the other students during the lectures which disturbed the teachers a lot. Some students come late for the lecture. They enter the class during the lecture it disturbed the teacher. The disturbance is the biggest problem mostly the teachers faced in teaching the English language.

Teaching English language is not an easy task, it requires the teachers to have ability to use methods and approaches and teaching supports. Teacher has to play many roles in the classroom. One side teachers have to focus on teaching the classes at understanding level of students. In other ways, they have to complete the syllabus given time and assess the learning of the students in the classroom. If classroom is observed, there can be find variation among the student's proficiency. Teachers necessary keep it mind before get ready lesson plan. Apart from that time factor and infrastructure, resources are mostly mandatory things for teaching language in the classroom. Language is not subject, like chemistry, mathematic but it is skill oriented where practice is needed to acquire skills of language. All main basic skills of language like Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing are integrated. Most of the studies conducted on the areas of methods of teaching, diagnosis the learning difficulties, teaching Grammar, Spelling, Pronunciation etc. However, few studies revealed that seniority of the teachers were not professionally equipped to teach English. Problems related to school facilities 20% of teachers have stated that the children do not have proper seating arrangements in the classrooms. Finally, if we think about these problems that as said at the top, in depth and find a broader solution, the challenges will disappear. These matters depend more on the government of education.

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